

REDUCING SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION THROUGH COGNITIVE INTERVENTIONS: A STUDY OF MINDFULNESS AND SOCIAL LEARNING IN SOKOTO STATE COLLEGES

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Abstract

This study investigated the comparative effectiveness of mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy in addressing social media addiction among students in tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Recognizing the growing prevalence of addictive social media behavior and its impact on academic performance and mental health, the study adopted a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design. A total of 40 students from two universities were selected using purposive sampling. The Social Media Addiction Questionnaire developed by Idiedo and Omamomo (2023), with a reliability index of 0.74, was adapted as the primary data collection instrument. The 20-item questionnaire employed a 4-point Likert scale to gauge levels of addiction.

Three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the investigation. The interventions were carried out separately using mindfulness-based techniques and social learning-based methods. Data were analyzed using the t-test to determine the significance of differences in addiction levels before and after treatment.

Findings revealed that mindfulness therapy alone did not significantly reduce social media addiction. In contrast, social learning therapy showed a statistically significant effect in reducing addiction among both male and female students. However, when comparing both interventions, results indicated that there was no significant difference in their overall effectiveness in reducing social media addiction. This suggests that while social learning therapy may produce more immediate observable results, both approaches can contribute positively to behavioral change over time.

The study concludes that both mindfulness and social learning therapies are viable tools for addressing excessive social media use among university students. It recommends the incorporation of these therapies by university counselors, lecturers, and student affairs professionals to foster healthier digital habits and promote positive behavioral transformation.

Keywords: Social Media Addiction, Mindfulness Therapy, Social Learning Therapy, Tertiary Institutions, Behavioral Intervention

Introduction

The world is enjoying improvement in communication technology which has improved communication through information and communication technology (ICT). In recent years, significant changes have taken place around the world regarding the expansion of internet and the number of people who use them through the internet, web technologies with regards to information sharing and communication have emerged, and one prominent technology is the social media (Mingle & Adams, 2015). Social media has become one of the most important

communication means which provides communication among people regardless of the distance, making it open to people to easily share information, files pictures, videos, create blogs and send messages as well as conduct real-time conversation. It is referred as social because it allows communication with friends, family and co-workers easily and effectively and as such, straighten ties and relationship between people (Na-jega & Lawal, 2020).

The use of social media is increasing in Nigeria and the world (Ersoz & Kahraman, 2020). According to Digital (2021), Global overview report that, the time spent on social media has increased 1.5 times in the last five (5) years. The youths are said to be the highest users of social media (Akintola, 2021). In recent years, the number of social media users in Nigeria has rise with more than 100 million registered users. And the most widely used social networks include: Facebook, Youtube, Whatsapp, Facebook Messenger, Instagram, Tik-Tok, Tumbler, Linkedin, We Chat, Q Zone, Baido Tieba and Twitter among others (Ofole, 2023). In 2021, Nigerians spent an average of 3 hours and 41 minutes on social media every day. This is significantly higher than the global average of 2 hours 22 minutes. Between January 2020 and January 2021, the number of active social media users in Nigeria increased by 22 percent compared with the global average increase of 13 per cent. As of 2022, social media users in the country reached roughly 34 million in total, expanding from the 18 million individuals registered in 2017. On the basis of this increasing trend keeps stable, it is expected that by 2025, over 90 million people will use at least one social media platform in Nigeria. Overall, the most followed network accounts are those of friends, family and people known by social media user. In the third quarter of 2021, Whatsapp was the most popular social media platform in Nigeria with over 90 million users. Facebook, Youtube and Instagram followed as the most used social media platforms in Nigeria. The number of Whatsapp users in Nigeria was forecast to continuously increase between 2022 and 2028 by 12.7 million users. According to this forecast in 2028, the Whatsapp users will have increased for the sixth consecutive years to 19.93 million users (Ofole, 2023). Though, these websites and social forums are ways of communicating directly with other people socially and in media. Thus, play a large and influential role in decision making in the global world economy, politics, social settings and education (Al-Rahmile & Othman in Na-jega & Lawal, 2020), Meanwhile, youths/ students use social media sites not only for leisure and personal socialization, but also as a platform for more meaningful and serious deliberations. Some students are using social media for making friends, sharing links, online learning (e-learning), it provides news update to students and informing them about their course activities. It aids teachers in communicating with students even when they are not in their classrooms. The use of platforms provides the students with unlimited resources and texts from credible sources that they can utilize to their advantage in presentations, projects, essay etc. It is also a means of giving and receiving feedbacks and means of finding jobs, while some students use social media in a negative way.

Dan'azumi (2024) added that, social media also exposes contents like pornography, violence, commercialism, cyber bullying, unsupervised social relations, privacy and security issues. Social media brings a lot of problems as it tends to consume individual's time. In most cases, youths are more affected as they have problem of adjusting to maintaining balance between practicing social networking and their academics. They tend to have little or no control over their urge to pick up their phones and socialize over the internet thereby reducing their interest into any academic activities and this may be termed as social media addiction (Dan'azumi, 2024).

Social Media

Social media are interactive technologies that facilitate the creation and sharing of contents, ideas, interests and other forms of expression through virtual communities and networks (Andrew, 2017). In addition, social media is a form of electronic communication such as websites for social networking and micro blocking through which users create online communities to share information, ideas, personal messages and other contents such as audios and videos. In other words, it is a form of expression between two or more people in an online matter, which the information may be negative or positive also, social media is a conduit for misleading information and falsehoods. Social media refers to an online facilitator or enhancer of human networks-webs of individuals who enhance social connectivity (Tuten, Tracy, Solomon, & Michael, 2018). It means any human communication or sharing of information on the internet that occurs through a computer, mobile phones or tablets. Users of social media usually access social media services through web-based applications on desktops or download services that offers functionality to these devices like smart phones and tablets (Tuten, Tracy, Solomon, & Michael, 2018).

Some of these types of social media as stated by Ibrahim (2016:43) include: social network site: such as facebook, whatsapp, linkedin and others. Media sharing sites allows the users to post videos or photographs and others can share, comment or like. Examples are; Youtube, Instagram, Tiktok and so on, status update services e.g Tweets, Blogs, Social Bookmarking: social bookmarking allows users to organize and share links to websites, virtual word content, Wikis (wikipedia) etc. The use of these social network sites is an ever-growing phenomenon most especially with the students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state. These network sites are taking much of students' time, attention and energy which could have been channeled toward their academic pursuits (Haustein & Stefanie, 2016).

Social Media Addiction

Social media addiction is a form of psychological or behavioural dependance on social media platforms (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017; Hogan & Strasburger, 2018). Social media can be diagnosed when an individual engages in online activities at the cost of fulfilling his daily responsibilities or pursuing other interest and without regard for negative consequences. Social media addiction is also exhibited in a situation where adolescent students uncontrollably and obsessively check and use the applications for a number of hours only chatting with peers or friends. Some may spend lengthy time only going through other people's profiles or unimportant post that may not improve

their academic status. Kuss and Griffiths (2017) added that, social media addict can be considered as one with an urge to use social media excessively. For instance, engaging in activities like frequently checking status, updates and post or stalking the profile of other users for many hours, and these behaviours or habits conflicts with his/her everyday responsibilities such as family, school, work or other social obligations.

Some of the major symptoms of social media addiction as identified by Ayelabowo (2019:294304) include: checking social media first thing in the morning and last thing at night, feeling stressed when the smart phone isn't at hand, using social media even while walking or eating, feeling unsettled when there is no access to the internet or when the social network is down or it is slower than usual.

The primary motivation for the cause of social media addiction is the feeling of gratification that it provides to the user (Andreassen & Pallesen, 2014). For example; when someone receives a notification, it makes him/her feel happy. Fear of missing out (FOMO) can also leads to compulsive checking of social media platforms to ensure that an individual is not missing out on anything which can cause problems in his/her learning process, academic achievement as well as impacting negatively in their real-life relationship making most people fall in to social media addiction (Casale, Rugai & Fioravanti, 2018). Secondly, it serves as a source for escapism; this referred to as a behaviour employed to distract oneself from real life problems. For instance, individuals sometimes tend to escape from unpleasant situations. Likewise, social media can act as either an escape from real-life trouble or to avoid thinking about unpleasant thoughts (Young, Kuss, Griffiths & Howard, 2017). Using social media can make people feel increasingly unhappy and isolated. These negative emotional reactions are not only produced due to the social pressure of sharing things with others but also the comparison of material things and lifestyle also increase risk of developing mental issues such as anxiety and depression that these sites promote (Sahin, 2017; Hawi & Samaha, 2017).

The effects of internet addiction according to Ekwelundu, Obi and Ofojebe (2023) may result to psychological, social and physical health problems such as; sleep deprivation, excessive fatigue, decreased immune system, lack of proper exercise, poor personal hygiene, back or eye stain, social isolation, lack of real-life social relationship, neglect of daily chores, increased family conflicts, academic problems, cyber bullying, sexual predators and exposure to pornographic materials. Bener, Al Mahdi and Ali (2011) added that social media addiction leads to overweight, obesity and impaired vision.

Bawa and Suleiman (2017) in their study social media addiction and academic engagement among undergraduate students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design with undergraduate students from Usmanu Danfodiyo University as the population of the study in four faculties using purposive sampling method. A sample size of 370 undergraduate students from the population of 12,3300 across the four faculties was used while simple random sampling was used to select the respondents. Instruments on social media addiction and academic engagement were used to secure responses of the respondents. The data

were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics and the findings revealed that; social media addiction level was high among undergraduate students and academic engagement was low. The study of Dakasku, Gambo and Musa (2023) on effects of motivational enhancement therapy on social media addiction among senior secondary school students in Damaturu metropolis, Yobe state, Nigeria. The study used quasi-experimental research design of pre-test, post-test type on 120 participants. Social media addiction scale with a reliability index of .89 was used in collecting data from the participants. Data was collected in four different but interconnected phases. T-test for independent sample was employed to test two hypotheses at .05 level of significance and the findings revealed that there was significant effects of motivational enhancement therapy on social media addiction among secondary school students, there is no significant difference in motivational enhancement therapy on social media addiction among secondary school students according to gender.

Ekwelundu, Obi and Ofojebe (2023) study on relative effectiveness of cognitive behavioural and reality therapies on internet addiction among secondary school students in Anambra state. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design on pre-test, post-test and control group on a sample population of 60 students from 3 public secondary schools in Anaocha Local Government area of Anambra State using purposive sampling technique. Simple random sampling was used to assign the participants into experimental and control group. The experimental procedures were carried out at in three phases of pre-treatment, treatment and post-treatment using two counselling therapies and placebo. The data collected was analyzed using statistical mean as well as analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The result of their study revealed that cognitive behavioural and reality therapies were effective in the treatment of internet addiction. Meanwhile, reality therapy was more effective than cognitive therapy in the treatment of internet addiction among secondary school adolescents in Anaocha Local Government area of Anambra State.

The work of Garba, Sababa and Aji (2023) on effects of Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) on Social Media Addiction among Tertiary Institution Students in Taraba state, Nigeria. The study employed a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test and control design on a population sample of 40 students from 11 tertiary institutions using purposive sampling technique. Social Media Addiction Test (SMAT) was used for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using ANCOVA. The results of the findings revealed that CBT has significant effects in reducing the level of social media addiction among tertiary institution students in Taraba state. The findings also revealed that the effects of CBT didn't vary with gender in all results.

Social learning theory is a of learning process on social behavior which proposes that new behaviors can be acquired by observing and imitating others. It states that learning is a cognitive process that takes place in a social context and can occur purely through observation or direct instruction, even in the absence of motor reproduction or direct reinforcement. In addition to the observation of behavior, learning also occurs through the observation of rewards and punishments, a process known as vicarious reinforcement. When a particular behavior is rewarded

regularly, it will most likely persist; conversely, if a particular behavior is constantly punished, it will most likely desist.

Addiction is related to the social learning theory as it emphasizes the role of social influences and reinforces the development and maintenance of addictive behaviors. The social learning theory suggests that people learn and adopt behaviors through observation, experience, and reinforcement from social interactions with others. In the case of addiction, individuals may learn and adopt substance use behaviors from peers, family members, or media exposure, and through positive reinforcement such as pleasure or relief from stress. The social learning theory proposes that addiction is a learned behavior influenced by environmental and social factors.

Mindfulness therapy is a versatile approach that can be used alongside many other therapy types for an eclectic mix or by itself as a standalone therapy. Based on Eastern practices, mindfulness is used in hospitals, schools, the military, and psychotherapy. Learning more about this technique can help you decide if it would be adequate for your needs. Mindfulness is a method of becoming more aware of yourself and your environment through sensory focus, structured thinking, breathing exercise, and other techniques. You can observe your thoughts, feelings, and physical sensations nonjudgmental through mindfulness. Mindfulness is set in the present moment, where you can consciously direct your awareness as it occurs. The study is linked to Gratification theory which was first developed in the 1940's by Lazarsfeld and Stanton 1944 who attempt to explain the reason why people use mass media and the different types of gratification they receive from it (satisfaction or reward obtained by individuals). And also, time displacement theory which was first discussed by Putnam (1995a), (1995b), who proposes that, people only have limited time and attention. Participation in one communication activity takes away from participation in another. The underlying assumption is that individuals have a limited amount of time which is seen as social capital and if they increase the time they spend on one activity, there will logically be sacrifices in other areas to compensate (Lee & Kuo, 2002). The displacement in this case occurs when students replace their academic pursuits for social media usage to the time which was previously allocated to more important things like social events, interpersonal communication, social movements, interaction with people, education and helping each other in social and personal matters. The gratification received in the use of social media include; need for identity, development of social identities, learning how to start and end relationship and acceptable types of humour (Valkenburg, Peter & Walther, 2016).

Statement of the Problem

Social media addiction has become a threat in the society. The rate at which youths especially the students of higher institutions in Sokoto state use social media is alarming and increasing day by day. This is because the use of social media has become an enormous part of people's daily lives and as such, most students/youths engage most of their precious time on social media. Even though, some of the youths who were addicted to social media usage may be using it wisely such as in research and seeking knowledge. But, majority of the students/ youths in

their higher education level, especially university students in Sokoto state abuse the use of social media and this may affect their psychological, social and physical health which includes: sleep deprivation, back or eye strain, lack of real life social relationship, lack of proper exercise, increase in family conflicts, lack of daily chores, social isolation, cyber bullying, decreased immune system, poor personal hygiene, sexual predators and exposure to pornographic materials and above all their academic performance.

These and many more reasons triggered the interest of the researchers in conducting this research by using counselling therapies such as social learning therapy and mindfulness therapy to see how effective these therapies will be helpful in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the effective use of mindfulness therapy in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender.
2. To examine the effective use of social learning therapy in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender.
3. To examine the difference between mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the research:

H₀₁: Mindfulness therapy has no significant effects on reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender

H₀₂: Social learning therapy has no significant effects on reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design of pretest-posttest type. The population of the study is the entire students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state which comprising the total of thirty-seven thousand two hundred and ninety-one (37,291) students. But for the purpose of this study, only two universities were selected to represent the population of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state using purposive sampling method. The justification for the selection of these two universities was to enable the researchers to carry out their research for effective and efficient result.

A sample of forty (40) students was used from the two Universities that were selected as the sample population of the study with twenty (20) students representing each of the institutions respectively using purposive sampling

technique. Simple random sampling was used to select and assign the subjects into the experimentation. The subjects were grouped into two (2) groups namely: Social learning therapy group and Mindfulness therapy group. Each group constituted of twenty (20) subjects to participate in the study, making the total forty (40) participants. The instrument used for data collection was adapted from Idiedo and Omamomo (2023) Social Media Addiction Questionnaire which was designed to show the level of social media addiction among university students. The instrument was divided into two sections; section A: deals with the demographic data of the students while section B: has twenty (20) items which sought information about social media addiction. The items were based on four (4) point likert scale with options like: SA= Strongly Agreed (4), A= Agreed (3), D= Disagree (2), SD=Strongly Disagreed (1). The values of 4,3,2,1 was assigned to represent their response respectively. The highest score is 80 while the lowest score is 20. As such, any student that score between 40-80 is said to have social media addiction while 39-20 are said to have fewer social media addiction. The validity and reliability of the instrument were ascertained by the original authors with a reliability index of 0.74 obtained.

Experimental Procedure

The study was carried out in three (3) phases (pre-treatment, treatment period and post- treatment period) within the period of four (4) sessions.

In phase one: General orientation, collection of baseline data and administration of Social Media Addiction Questionnaire (SMAQ) was done to all the subjects in the two (2) groups ie. Social learning Therapy, Mindfulness Therapy for pre-test. In phase two; which was the treatment period for Social Media Addiction (SMA), each session for the two treatment groups social learning therapy and mindfulness therapy for (SMA) met once in a week for three (3) weeks for a period of 40minutes to 1hour per session per week. In phase three, post-test was administered after the conclusion of the session to examine if the experimental treatment conditions provided a change or not.

Synopsis of the treatment packages was given below:

Session one: General orientation, collection of baseline data and administration of social media addiction questionnaire to obtain pre-test scores from the subjects.

Session two: The treatment period; the subjects were grouped in to mindfulness therapy group and social learning therapy group with each researcher attending to one group. For mindfulness therapy group; the researcher started with discussing issues of social media platforms and social media addiction. The researcher also injected the values of mindfulness through explaining the appropriate use of social media and time management so as to awaken their mode of thinking on the use of social media. Using mindfulness to explain and describe the negative effects of excessive use of social media on personal health and values were also brought forward so as to awaken their mode of thinking on the use of social media reflecting the idea of being minding of what they are doing. While for social learning therapy; the researcher starts by discussing social media and elaborating on social media

addiction as well as some major facts about excessive use of social media on an unproductive way which has negative effects on personal health, academic and moral value as well. The researcher through social learning therapy try to influence students on the appropriate use of social media on a productive channel, personal growth and development for brighter future through imitation, learning and observation so as to emulate successful icons who have successfully registered their achievement through the appropriate use of social media.

Session three: For mindfulness therapy group; the researcher asked the students to use 20minutes and reflects on how they use social media (meditation). This procedure will enable the students to see and accepts positive or negative attributes the use of social media has caused him/her to attain changes by being mindful of how to use social media positively. While for social learning therapy group; the researcher focused on the use of social media in achieving gratification. Social learning explains that, some students use some social media platforms such as status viewing, un productive chatting, watching porn videos and pictures for gratification for example; to ease tension (unpleasant situation), they should rather channel their use of social media to progressive, productive and achievement activities such as learning, business meetings, advertising, innovative creativity and development of moral values among others.

Session four: This is the last session for the treatment. Summary of mindfulness therapy & social learning therapy was given by the researchers and the re-administration of social media addiction instrument to the subjects for post-test score and formal closing of the sessions.

The data obtained from the students for the three hypotheses raised were analyzed using statistical mean and standard deviation of t-test analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.5 level of significance.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: Mindfulness therapy has no significant effect in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender.

This hypothesis was tested by subjecting the social media addiction post-test scores of the male and female students exposed to mindfulness therapy to a t-test analysis and the result was presented in table 1.

Table 1: Effect of Mindfulness Therapy in the Reduction of Social Media Addiction among Male and Female Students.

Variables	N	Mean Rank	Std. Deviation	U	p-Value	Decision
Male	8	10.50	6.476	48.000	1.00	H ₀ Accepted
Female	12	10.50	.503			

Result of table 1 indicates that significant effect of mindfulness therapy of the male (Mean = 12.92) and of the female (Mean = 6.88) in the reduction of social media addiction of students is positive and significant, $U = 48.00$, $p = 1.00$, Since the p-value is more than the .05 level of significance, therefore H_{01} which states that mindfulness therapy has no significant effect in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender was accepted. This implies that, mindfulness therapy was not significantly effective in reducing social media addiction among male and female students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state as male students are more mindful on social media usage than female students.

H_{02} : Social learning therapy has no significant effect in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender.

This hypothesis was tested by subjecting the social media addiction post-test scores of the male and female students exposed to social learning therapy to a t-test analysis and the result was presented in table 2.

Table 2: Effect of Social Learning Therapy in the Reduction of Social Media Addiction among Male and Female Students.

Variables	N	Mean Rank	Std. Deviation	U	p-Value	Decision
Male	12	12.92	8.736	19.00	.025	H_0 Rejected
Female	8	6.88	.503			

Result of table 2 indicates that significant effect of social learning therapy of the male (Mean = 12.92) and of the female (Mean = 6.88) in the reduction of social media addiction of students is positive and significant, $U = 19.00$, $p = .025$, Since the p-value is less than the .05 level of significance, therefore H_{02} which states that social learning therapy has no significant effect in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender was rejected. This implies that; social learning therapy was effective in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

H_{03} : There is no significant difference between mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

This hypothesis was tested by subjecting the social media addiction post test scores of students exposed to mindfulness therapy and those exposed to social learning therapy to a t-test analysis and the result was presented in table 3.

Table 3: Difference in the Reduction of Social Media Addiction between Students Exposed to Mindfulness Therapy and those Exposed to Social Learning Therapy.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Mindfulness	20	48.45	6.476	.596	.559	H ₀
Social Learning	20	47.00	8.736			Accepted

Result of table 3 indicates that no significant difference exist between students exposed to mindfulness therapy (Mean = 48.45) and those exposed to social learning therapy (Mean = 47.00), and though positive, is not significant, $t(19) = .559$, $p = .000$ and also that the p-value is more than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, H₀₃ which states that there is no significant difference between mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state was accepted.

This implies that, both mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy were effective both not significantly different in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of hypothesis one revealed that mindfulness therapy has no significant effect in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender. The finding of the study is in line with the findings of Mahomet and Ali in Dan-azumi (2024) where their results revealed that social media addiction level of the male students is higher compared to that of the female students; this is caused by the social roles imposed on men and women depending on social status and responsibilities and cultural structure, and as a number of days and hours spent on social media increase, so does the addiction to social media.

The finding is supported by the theory of time displacement which explains how students use social media excessively, displacing more important commitments like studying, interpersonal communication, interaction with people, education and helping each other in social and personal matters to chatting and watching films etc. Findings of hypothesis two revealed that social learning therapy has significant effect in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state by gender was rejected. This finding is in line with the study of Dakasku, Gambo and Musa (2023) whose findings revealed significant effects of motivational enhancement therapy on social media addiction among secondary school students and no significant difference in motivational enhancement therapy on social media addiction among secondary school students according to gender. Their study concluded that motivational enhancement therapy is effective in reducing social media addictive behavior such as salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict and relapse. The finding is hinged on gratification theory which explained the reasons why people engage into various forms of social

media and the different types of gratification they receive from it. Finding of hypothesis three revealed that both mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy are effective and not significantly different in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state. This finding is in line with the study of Ekwelundu, Obi and Ofojebe (2023) whose findings revealed that counselling therapies such as cognitive behavioural and reality therapies were effective in the treatment of internet addiction. Meanwhile, reality therapy was more effective than cognitive therapy in the treatment of internet addiction among secondary school adolescents in Anaocha Local Government area of Anambra State. The finding is supported by gratification and time displacement theories where both mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy were found to be effective and not significantly different in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was revealed that, mindfulness therapy was not significantly effective in reducing social media addiction among male and female students while social learning therapy was effective in reducing social media addiction among male and female students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state. This indicates that, male and female students were not mindful of the excessive way they use social media and the consequences attached to it as it may affect their academic performance, their psychological (health) and social interaction. The finding also revealed that both mindfulness therapy and social learning therapy were effective and not significantly different in reducing social media addiction among students of tertiary institutions in Sokoto state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Students should realize that, excessive social media usage has effects on their health and social life. Therefore, they should be mindful of how they use it and the consequences attached to the outcome.
2. Social learning therapy should be employed by counsellors and lecturers at various institutions in creating more awareness for students on the appropriate way to use social media in a productive manner.
3. Lecturers can adopt both social learning and mindfulness therapies in making reference to having a successful positive behavioural change among students.

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